

THE APPLICATION OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AT HUFU

Duong Thi Bich Dao

Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry

Email: daodtb@cntp.edu.vn

ABSTRACT

Technology has played a vital role in learning and teaching English around the world. The role and status of English in HUFU or Vietnamese Universities can be seen as a key subject of curriculum. Today, there are a lot of things to choose from the world of technology: Videos, DVD's, the Internet, Email, Audio Cassettes, Blogs, Computers and CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning)... for teaching and learning English language. The rapid development of information technology has given the new teaching models. Therefore, this article deals with the application of multimedia technology in English language teaching for non-major students in Vietnamese universities and the problems that the teachers and learners faced when using multimedia technology. In addition, it also aims to make teachers aware of the strategies to use it in an effective way.

Key words: English language teaching, Multimedia technology, Advantages, Disadvantages, Optimization, Strategies.

1 INTRODUCTION

English is an international language, so the development of English is necessary in Vietnam's universities as well as in Ho Chi Minh University of Food Industry. Using computers and Internet in classes in general today and in language classes in particular is very common. At present, the role of English in Vietnamese Universities is higher than ever. Its position is as a key subject of medium of introduction and curriculum. So, the different teaching methods have been implemented to experiment the effectiveness of the English language teaching. The use of technology in the forms of tape recording, radio, television, films has been there for a long time. These technologies have proved to be successful in replacing the traditional teaching. The language teachers have new challenges and duties nowadays. Traditional English teaching has been changed with the remarkable development of newer technology. Technology has many options that we can choose to teach in order to make teaching and productive more attractive for English learners as David Graddol: (1997:16) states that "technology lies at the heart of the globalization process; affecting education work and culture". Learning English is more and more developed in Vietnam in general and in Universities in particular. The language teachers use

different methods and one of the effective methods is the use of technology in teaching language to create English contexts. It helps students to get involved and learn effectively.

2 THE USE OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING

English is more and more popular in Vietnam as well as in the world, so the language teaching methods need to be changed in order to meet the development of science and technology. Today, there are many opportunities for students in HUFU and other Universities to gain confidence in learning English because of applying multimedia technology. It is proved that multimedia technology plays a positive role in promoting activities and initiatives for students and teaching effectively in English class.

The age of globalization and information technology in the twenty-first century as Harry Samuels argues, “Much more recent developments in social media and information technology are taking foreign- language education in new directions”. English is one of the important mediums of communication in the world. In HUFU as well as Vietnam’s Universities, English language teaching is also one of the important subjects in education. With the rapid growth of science and technology, the use of multimedia technology and its application in language teaching has created a favourable platform for reforming and exploring English teaching model in the new era. The highlight of the trends is using audio, visual, and animation effects in English language teaching classrooms. The technological innovations should go hand in hand with the growth of English and are changing the way in which we communicate. In fact, the growth of the internet has facilitated the growth of the English language. In this sense, computers are no longer the exclusive domains of a few individuals, but rather they are available to many. When English language teaching models change rapidly, there has been a very significant proliferation of literature regarding the use of technology as the most essential part in teaching. Such a tendency has emphasized on an essential role of technology in pedagogy in which technology has been dominant over the teacher. The teachers will never be able to catch up with the new trend if they ignore technological developments. As Rana said, “Teachers need to stop following the same old ways of teaching and experiment and acknowledge that the world is changing, and we need education that augment that change”. For this reason, it is important for language to be aware of the latest and best equipment and to have a full knowledge of what is available in any given situation.

There are many techniques that we can apply in various forms in English language teaching situation to create more colourful and stimulate language classes. Some are useful for testing and distance education and some for teaching business English, spoken English, reading, listening... The teaching principle needs to appreciate new technologies and functions and do not let machines take over the role of the teacher or limit functions in which traditional ways are superior. That’s why all language learners and teachers must know how to make the use of the new technology.

3 ADVANTAGES OF USING MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGY

When multimedia technology becomes available to all of us, the language teachers should integrate into their lessons and give assessment planning in the same way they have been doing with film, computer assisted learning strategies... The students are reached to new technologies that provide interesting and new approaches for language teaching and learning. In this way, English teachers take a lot of advantages of technology to teach English for students in HUFU or Vietnam's Universities or non-native speaking learners. The important advantages of using multimedia technology are mentioned below:

3.1 Motivating students to learn English through Multimedia Technology

Now, multimedia technology with the help of audio, visual and animation effects, motivates the students to learn English quickly and effectively. Multimedia enables learning through exploration, discovery and experience. With multimedia, the process of learning can become more and more oriented, flexible in time and space and can increase collaboration between teachers and students. Multimedia enables learning to become fun and friendly.

The following is the description study based on a questionnaire that was prepared for specific purpose and was administered to 100 students for the second-year bachelor's degree at Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry. The questionnaire was composed of ten questions about motivation and technology use in EFL classrooms. (*See Appendix*)

According to the findings, students believe that the technology used in EFL classroom motivated them and 100% think that technology always increased their motivation in learning EFL. In total, 89% of the students believe that EFL would be improved if technology was used for every lesson. In total, 80% of the students believe that what teachers download from the internet is effective, but 20% the students think that it is ineffective because they think that sometimes this material negatively affects to their learning process and authentic materials can not completely replace teachers in class. Additionally, 92% of the students believe that the computer-based classroom make lesson more enjoyable and agree that multimedia technology provides students with ability to understand the lectures better. To improve student's understanding and learning process in EFL, 87% the students want to see different technological devices used for motivation. Almost of the students agree that lessons and lectures can be more enjoyable with Power Point presentation and have no difficulties in understanding these presentations. 70% of the students think that using technology every time make lessons interesting due to the different ways used to present lectures and the visual aids used in teaching. All of the students agree that tutorial videos often make lectures easy to understand because the videos and give several practice ways of how to act or solve problems in EFL. Just 60% of the students agree projects should be presented using multimedia technology. At last, all of students agree that computer-based lessons are more enjoyable and effective than traditional lesson.

In conclusion, the use of multimedia technology in EFL classroom provide a meaningful and interesting process by this technology development in EFL classroom.

3.2 Developing Students' Communicative Competence through Multimedia technology

It is difficult to achieve the goal of learning English language through the traditional teaching because it prevents the capacity of the students to understand the structures, meaning and function of the language and make the students passive in classroom learning activities.

In HUFU, with the using multimedia-assisted English language speaking and presentation practice, students can improve their pronunciation, intonation and rhythm of English speech and develop better oral skills and this technique could be regarded as an important tool in foreign language learning and teaching. Utilization of multimedia technology makes students more enjoyable and stimulating, for example, using Power Point template activates students' thinking and capacity to comprehend the language. Its audio and visual effects help students transform English learning into capacity cultivation. It creates a positive environment for the classroom's activities such as group discussion and debates that offer lots of chances for communication among students and between teachers and students. So, multimedia technology encourages students having positive thinking and communicative skills in learning a language.

3.3 Improving teaching efficiency by using multimedia technology

Using multimedia technology in the language classroom creates more real life environment for English teaching. It stimulates students' initiatives and economizes time in class and teachers can impart much more knowledge to the students. In big classes, it is hard for the students to have speaking communication, but the utilization of multimedia sound laboratories can solve this teaching problem. In addition, multimedia teaching enriches teaching contents and fundamentally improves class efficiency. Meanwhile, the traditional teaching method only emphasized on teacher's instruction and is limited about the information that students are provided by the teachers.

3.4 Enhancing Interaction among students and between teachers and students

Using multimedia technology empowers educational process by means of increased interaction between teachers and students. In the course of practice, students can understand deeply the material being taught. Teachers in the classroom no longer have difficulties to input information and force students to receive it in a passive way. Multimedia technology in teaching focuses on the active participation of the students and promotes the important interaction among the students and teachers. One of the main uses multimedia technology is to improve listening and speaking skills for the students. From there, students can develop their communicative competence. The utilization of multimedia technology can also create a context for the exchange information among the students and between the teachers and students.

3.5 Creating a favourable teaching environment in the classrooms

Teachers can create an environment for teaching a language by giving a context. This helps students lively and interesting and motivates students to participate in the classroom's activities. In the process of teaching English with multimedia technology, pictures and sound can be used to enhance the initiative for both teachers and students. When using multimedia software, teachers can use sound, image, pictures to enrich the content of the class. Moreover, teachers can show pictures and images of native speaking situations to enrich the sharing of information effectively. Using multimedia technology is to cultivate student's interest in learning and to improve the teacher's interest in teaching.

3.6 Giving opportunities for English teaching outside the classroom through multimedia technology

Teaching English with multimedia technology is flexible. With only a smartphone, technology can deliver contents in many ways. Teachers can use multimedia technology to deliver in advance, motivate learning with multiple channels of communications and construct assignments that force the students to prepare for class. Email can be used for assignments or reminder to students. Multimedia technology provide opportunities to have English teaching not only within the classroom situation but also outside the classroom situation. Teaching should be handled by the teacher, but it should be student-centered.

4 DISADVANTAGES OF USING MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGY

Multimedia teaching has the advantages that traditional teaching model can't compare it but it has some disadvantages also. They are listed as follows:

4.1 Informative but can not highlight the importance

Compared with the traditional teaching mode, one of the advantages of multimedia teaching is informative, but in practical teaching process, some of the teachers ignored the importance of classroom teaching during designing the courseware which results in excessive information but can not highlight the importance. In addition, the messages are often used on the courseware without a word to refine that the teachers downloaded abundant of information relevant the text. Moreover, some teachers ignored the importance of the students understanding and can not control the rhythm of the lecture's demonstration. For some students, they can not keep up with the lectures and they can not understand and digest them.

4.2 Lack of interactive exercises

Lacking openness and interactive activities make input and output imbalance. Though the use of multimedia technology in language classroom enhances the interest of students through audio, visual and textual affects upon the students, it lacks interactions among the students and between the teachers and students. Computer sound is gradually replaced the teacher's voice and visual

image is replaced the teacher's analysis. Therefore, the students will be limited in speaking communication. The sound and image of multimedia technology affect the students' initiative to think and speak.

4.3 Loss of students' logical thinking

The use of multimedia technology in teaching makes the students understand the content more easily but the abstract thinking would be restricted and from there their logical thinking would be faded away. The teachers should understand knowledge of something from perceptual recognition to rational apprehension is very important in the students' learning process. So, if the students only receive the images on the screen, their abstract thinking would be restricted, and logical thinking would be faded away. Multimedia technology needs to be used as an assisted tool for teaching a language and should not replace the dominant role of the teachers.

4.4 Lack of Real-time teaching to the classroom

Some teachers with the support of multimedia technology, prepare the pre-arranged courseware for the language teaching that lacks real-time effect to the classroom and students are unable to give feedback to the teachers. It's not good to develop spontaneity in thinking, in strengthening learning capacity and solving problems from the students. Thus, the cultivation of students' thinking capacity should be an important objective in teaching and using multimedia technology.

5 SUGGESTIONS AND STRATEGIES TO THE EXISTING PROBLEMS

In practical teaching, it is improper to copy the textual materials simply to the screen so that teacher's position is ignored. To ensure the function of multimedia technology in teaching, it should be noted that:

5.1 Teachers should play the leading role in teaching

The adequate application of multimedia technology in teaching can make breakthroughs in class teaching. That means, during multimedia assisting teaching, teachers still play the leading role and their role could not be replaced by the computer, for example, the introduction for each lesson and speaking communication are good ways to improve students' listening and speaking which computer cannot fulfil. English should be used frequently in the language classes to make the communication of the students better. Therefore, teachers should determine whether multimedia technology to adopt in English language teaching or not. Otherwise, the teachers were acting as projectionist, just clicking the screen.

5.2 The computer screen cannot be replaced the blackboard or whiteboard

Some of the teachers used the computer screen as the blackboard or whiteboard in teaching. They show exercises, questions, answers and teaching plans in piece by piece on the screen. They do not write anything on the blackboard. So, it's not a good ways to motivate the students

communicate in English because the teachers are supposed to stimulate situations based on teaching and guiding the students. Teachers should combine traditional and modern ways of language teaching in order to create a real-life context for effective teaching. Moreover, the experienced teachers know how a perfect teaching is and they had an ideal project in mind and need to enrich the contents on the blackboard with the new questions raised by the students.

5.3 Multimedia technology should not be overused

Some teachers think that applying totally multimedia technology in their teaching may give better performance in language teaching, create better class environment, motivate the students to participate in the class and help students access to the language materials. Apparently, the students show some interests in learning, but, they feel like looking on and inactive all the time. This kind of process ignores other skills in language teaching. If the students are interfered in inputting information, the students will take less from the language materials. It is impossible to train effectively the language expression of the students in class. Though, advantages of applying multimedia technology assist in teaching. In practice, if multimedia technology is utilized properly in English teaching without being overused, the students can develop the benefit use in English speaking, listening materials and improve their overall language skills. It leads to introduce multimedia technology to modern teaching in teaching listening, speaking, reading, reading and writing for the students and make the instructions of the teachers.

6 CONCLUSION

Using multimedia technology is one of the important parts in teaching English. It is to promote students' motivation and learning interest in the English language. Students in HUFU or Vietnam's Universities, English speaking context can be a practical way to get them involved in the language teaching. In order to achieve the goal, the language teachers need to create a favourable environment for English language teaching based on availability of information and teaching materials. The process of English learning should be more student-centered and less time - consuming. Application of multimedia technology can develop thinking and practical language skills and used effectively English teaching classroom.

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APPENDIX

The questionnaire was as followings

No.	Questionnaire	Agree	Disagree
1.	Are the multimedia technology used in your classroom motivate you about EFL?		
2.	Should multimedia technology be used for every lesson?		
3.	Are authentic materials downloaded from the internet and used by teachers make the learning process active?		
4.	Do computer-based teaching activities make lessons more enjoyable?		
5.	Do you think that technological devices should always be used in EFL classroom to increase your motivation?		
6.	Do lectures seem more interesting and enjoyable when the teacher uses PowerPoint presentation?		
7.	Does using multimedia technology every time make lessons interesting?		
8.	Do you think that tutorial video, films and CDs can be helpful developing EFL skills?		
9.	Do you think that projects should be presented using multimedia technology?		
10.	Do you think that computer-based lessons are more enjoyable and effective than traditional lesson?		